

Studies on Dithiocarbamates: Part X*. Synthesis and Spectral Characteristics of Mesoionic 4-phenyl-5-aryl-1,3,4,-thiadiazoles

P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta

A series of the titled compounds have been synthesized with well-behaved *meta* and *para*-substituents on the phenyl ring at C₅ and their spectral data on long wavelength $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as well as the stretching frequency of C-S band have been examined in the light of linear free energy relationship. Thus, Hammett $\sigma\rho$ relation was valid only with exalted values for NO₂ and CN groups indicating appreciable inter-nuclear conjugation, comparable to biphenyl system, between the planar mesoionic ring and the phenyl ring at C₅. Strong dipolar interactions in solution have been demonstrated by the use of solvents of graded polarity.

In the UV region λ_{\max} around 275 and 250 $m\mu$ have been assigned to phenyl groups at N₄ and C₅ respectively.

Recent physical measurements on mesoionic compounds^{1,2} like sydnone (I), isosydnone (II), 1,3,4-thiadiazole (III), and in particular MO calculations³ on I and II, tend to confirm the presence of delocalised sextet of π -electrons in these systems with considerable amount of resonance energy. But mesoionic thiadiazoles (III), particularly attractive as medicinal compounds, are frequently encountered to contain =NC(S)-fragment as a part of their structures. Our interest in III, therefore, largely stems from our current studies⁴ on physico-chemical properties of heterocyclic systems derived through dithiocarbamate or dithiocarbazinate.

The reported⁵ compounds are mostly 4-phenyl-5-alkyl types and only a few 4,5-diaryl types are known. For reasons stated in the sequel, a series of 4-phenyl-5-aryl types are reported here with particular attention on the type of a polar substituent on Ar. The thiadiazoles (III) were all synthesized by adding the appropriate aroyl chloride under agitation at room temperature to an aqueous solution of potassium phenyldithiocarbazinate as described by Stewart and Kier⁵. The experimental results are summarized in Table I.

* Preliminary Communication, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 356.

1. L. B. Kier and E. B. Roche, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1967, **56**, 149.
2. F. H. C. Stewart, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 129.
3. L. B. Kier and E. B. Roche, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1966, **55**, 807.
4. P. B. Talukdar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 17; P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *ibid.*, 1967, **44**, 104; P. B. Talukdar and S. Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1967, **44**, 1060.
- 5(a). T. G. Stewart and L. B. Kier, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, **54**, 731.
- (b). M. Ohta, H. Kato and T. Kaneko, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Jap.*, 1967, **40**, 579.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

M.p.s. are uncorrected.

Preparation of 4-phenyl-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (III): A typical preparation⁵ is briefly described below :

The appropriate aroyl chloride was first made from the acid (0.01 mole) and thionyl chloride and this was purified by extraction with dry hexane. After stripping off the solvent, the acid chloride was directly added, at a rate of 3 drops/min., at room temperature to an aqueous solution of potassium phenyldithiocarbazinate (2.2 g., 0.01 mole). The solution was vigorously agitated during the addition of acid chloride and stirring was continued for 30 min., more after complete addition of the acid chloride.

The separated gum was washed with 5% aq. NaHCO₃ and water. On trituration with 90% ethanol the desired crystalline material was obtained. Analytical samples were usually prepared by subsequent crystallisation from ethanol (90%)-acetone mixture. Relevant data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Mesoionic 4-Ph-5-Aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (III ; R = Ph, R₁ = Aryl)

Compound(III) Ar	M.p. °C	Mol. Form	Analysis	
			Found	Reqd. %
1. <i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	212-13d	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C, 53.51 H, 2.82	53.33 2.86
2. <i>p</i> -CNPh	250	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	C, 61.35 H, 2.99	61.02 3.05
3. <i>p</i> -IPh	219d.	C ₁₄ H ₉ IN ₂ S ₂	C, 42.57 H, 2.42	42.42 2.27
4. <i>p</i> -BrPh	212-13	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₂ S ₂	C, 48.10 H, 2.38	48.13 2.57
5. <i>p</i> -MePh	231-32	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	C, 63.29 H, 4.20	63.38 4.22
6. <i>p</i> -MeOPh	227-28a	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS ₂	N, 9.27	9.33
7. Ph	228a	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	N, 10.52	10.37
8. <i>m</i> -NO ₂ Ph	227-28	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C, 53.32 H, 2.94	53.33 2.86
9. <i>m</i> -IPh	212-13	C ₁₄ H ₉ IN ₂ S ₂	C, 42.49 H, 2.25	42.42 2.27
10. <i>m</i> -BrPh	195-96	C ₁₄ H ₉ BrN ₂ S ₂	C, 48.24 H, 2.52	48.13 2.57
11. <i>m</i> -ClPh	191-92	C ₁₄ H ₉ ClN ₂ S ₂	C, 54.73 H, 3.02	55.17 2.95
12. <i>m</i> -EtOPh	185	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS ₂	C, 60.92 H, 4.65	61.14 4.45

(a) Lit⁵. m.p. 228-29°

(b) Lit⁵. m.p. 228-29°

The compounds are orange to orange-yellow in colour and were obtained in 15–20% yield. In general, the compounds are more soluble in polar solvents like acetone and chloroform, practically insoluble in non-polar solvents like carbon tetrachloride and hexane.

Spectral measurements : The absorption spectra were recorded at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$) with a Hilger automatic recording spectrophotometer, which was calibrated before and after the measurements with a Holmium glass filter at 250 and 400 $m\mu$. The wavelengths are accurate to $\pm 1 m\mu$.

In all cases, reagent grade solvents were freshly distilled for making the solutions. The oscillator strength for the visible band was calculated from the following equation,

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon d\nu, \text{ utilising } \epsilon_{max} \Delta\nu \equiv \int \epsilon d\nu,$$

where $\Delta\nu$ is the wave number of the half band width. Transition energy (ΔE_T) was calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta E_T = 286 \times 10^3 / \text{\AA}.$$

Calculated values for ΔE_T and their differences ($\Delta\Delta E$) (solute-solvent interaction) between cyclohexane and other solvents are summarised in Tables II and III.

IR data were recorded in chloroform with Perkin-Elmer model 21 spectrophotometer.

TABLE II

Spectral data on mesoionic 1,3,4-thiadiazoles

Compd. Ar.	λ_{max}^{MeOH} $m\mu(\epsilon \times 10^{-3})$	$\epsilon \sim 275$	Oscillator Strength(f)	IR(cm^{-1}) C-S band
		$\epsilon\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$		
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	274(28.98); 428(5.51)	5.26	0.105	1324
<i>p</i> -CN-Ph	223.5(12.44); 263(25.88); 420(5.35)	4.84	0.144	1326
<i>p</i> -IPh	~250(16.29)*; 284(20.32); 405(6.29)	3.23	0.149	1329
<i>p</i> -BrPh	~254(18.74)*; 280(22.05); 405(5.89)	3.74	0.152	1330
<i>p</i> -ClPh ^a	405	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -MePh	225(13.80); ~247(13.86)*; 281(19.52); 397(5.87)	3.32	0.133	1332
<i>p</i> -MeOPh ^b	~231(15.43); ~245(14.75)*; 278(14.86); 395(7.14)	—	0.155	—
Pha	~248(15.23)*; 275(19.82); 397(5.24)	3.78	0.152	1332
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ Ph	252(24.54); ~280(18.38)*; 410(4.46)	4.12	0.109	1328
<i>m</i> -IPh	237(22.57); ~274(18.22)*; 405(5.01)	3.63	0.119	—
<i>m</i> -BrPh	~254(18.39)*; 273(19.92); 405(5.83)	3.74	0.120	1329
<i>m</i> -Cl Ph	~254(17.36)*; 273(18.73); 405(4.87)	3.84	0.114	1329
<i>m</i> -EtOPh	225(18.45); 248(17.85); 278(17.27); 397(5.59)	3.09	0.173	—

* Shoulder.

(a) Assumed¹ by analogy with other *p*-halo-compds.; reported⁵ λ_{max} is 410 $m\mu$ (EtOH).

(b) Reported^{1,5} λ_{max}^{EtOH} 233 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 14,600), 279 $m\mu$ (ϵ 14,200) and 403 $m\mu$ (ϵ 4400).

(c) Reported^{n,5} λ_{max}^{EtOH} 275 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 18,900), 405 $m\mu$ (ϵ , 4600).

TABLE III

Solvent Effect on the visible band of 4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (III, R = R₁ = Ph)

Solvent	Dielectric constant ^a	Z-values KCal/mole	λ_{max} (m μ)	ϵ_{max}	ΔE_T Kcal/mole	$\Delta \Delta E$ Kcal/mole
1. Methanol	31.0	83.6	397	5240	72.04	7.62
2. Isopropanol	26.0	76.3	412	4388	69.42	5.00
3. Acetonitrile	37.5	71.3	410	5265	69.76	5.34
4. Acetone	20.7	65.7	420	4956	68.11	3.69
5. Chloroform	4.9	63.2	428	5043	66.83	2.41
6. Acetone-cyclo-hexane mixt.						
50% v/v acetone	—	—	430	4634	66.51	
30% v/v ..	—	—	434	4412	65.91	
20% v/v ..	—	—	437	4086	65.45	
10% v/v ..	—	—	440	3375	65.00	
7. Cyclohexane ^a	2.0	—	442	—	64.42	

(^a) Data taken from Techniques of Organic Chemistry, Vol. VII, Organic Solvents, Ed. by A. Weissberger, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1955.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visible band : Hammick and Voaden⁶ pointed out that the sydnone ring is characterised by a single peak at the 290–350 m μ region. Isosydrones (II) also practically absorb in the same region⁷. But the mesoionic thiadiazoles (III) exhibit a characteristic long wave length band around 400 m μ . This is not unexpected owing to substantial difference in electronegativity between oxygen and sulphur.

But examination of published¹ data in conjunction with ours (Table II), clearly demonstrates increased electron delocalisation through C₅ in III. In this context, it is tempting to examine the extent of internuclear conjugation in 5-aryl derivatives of III as in the case of biphenyl derivatives. The effect of substituents on the characteristic band ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) has been therefore examined in a standard manner by taking a series of appropriately substituted aryl groups at C₅ in III.

Substituent Effect : Inspection of data (Table II) clearly shows that the substituents indeed influence the position and intensity (*f*) of λ_{max} . But strongly electron demanding group like *p*-NO₂, as usual, shows the largest red shift (31 m μ) compared to the unsubstituted compound; and the shift is only moderate (\sim 8 m μ) with the halogenated derivatives. As anticipated, only a marginal change could be discerned with electron donating alkoxy groups. A fair amount of red shift with the *meta*-NO₂ derivatives suggests that strong resonance interaction could operate even by a relay system.

6. D. L. Hammick and D. J. Voaden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3303.

7. C. Anisworth, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, 43, 1607.

Presumably, dipolar structures like V must contribute appreciably at the excited state when the excess π -electron density at the *para*-position (Va) should be better accommodated by a nitro group than the halogens in the same position. Consequently, electron

releasing groups in the same position would tend to oppose this operation leading to the observed effect on the absorption spectra. It is therefore expected that the resonance parameters of the substituents would play a predominant role with the extent of shift in λ_{max} . Indeed, fairly good linear relationship between λ_{max} or $1/\lambda_{max}$ (which is proportional to transitional energy) against Hammett σ constants^{9,10} gave the best fit (Fig. 1) only with enhanced values for nitro and cyano groups and the corresponding equations for regression lines are as follows :

$$\lambda_{max} = 398.398(\pm 4.586) m\mu + 21.08\sigma; \quad r = 0.974$$

and

$$10^4/\lambda_{max} = 25.093(\pm 0.015) - 1.253\sigma; \quad r = 0.975.$$

Fig. 1—Hammett plots of $1/\lambda_{max}$ and λ_{max} against σ values.

But the use of σ^n or σ^0 constants⁹, where the inductive component is emphasised, leads to more scattering of points (not shown), though fairly good linear relationship could be noticed with *para*-substituents only. Similarly, serious difficulties arise with Taft σ_R constants¹⁰ when opposing trends of the donor and acceptor groups are reflected by the tendency

8. H. H. Jaffe', *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **53**, 191.
9. P. R. Wells, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 171.
10. R. W. Taft, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1805; R. W. Taft in *Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry*, Ed. by M. S. Newman, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1956, p. 556, cf. D. L. Ross and E. Reissner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2571.

to form a peak with the unsubstituted compound at the apex. However, perfectly linear alignment of the *p*-nitro, *p*-cyano and *m*-nitro derivatives is of special significance. In other words, the balance of inductive and resonance parameters of the substituents could only account for the observed shift in λ_{\max} , and direct resonance interaction is predominant only in a few instances of which *m*-nitro derivative is the most single impressive illustration. The magnitude and sign of $\rho(-1.253)$ is also in keeping with the notion that charge delocalisation at the excited state mainly involve species as depicted in V.

We are, therefore, inclined to believe that internuclear conjugation between the planer mesoionic ring and the 5-aryl group occurs to an appreciable extent, otherwise, extrathermodynamic relationship¹¹ is expected to breakdown. Further it is interesting to observe that the calculated¹² angle of twist for III (R = Ph, R₁ = *O*-ClPh) ($\theta = 26^\circ$) is quite close to that in biphenyl¹³ ($\theta = 23^\circ$).

IR Spectra : The mesoionic thiadiazoles (III) are reported⁵ to exhibit a characteristic C-S stretching band around 1330 cm⁻¹. The compounds reported here also exhibit similar bands as recorded in Table II. Besides, we invariably noticed splitting of this band as shown in Fig. 2. By analogy with sydnones, this phenomenon may be ascribed to Fermi resonance¹⁴.

But the interesting feature of our results is the impact of substituents on the C₅-aryl group on the frequency of the C-S band. In fact Hammett $\sigma\rho$ relationship was found to hold good¹⁵ between the C-S group frequencies and the substituent constants (σ or σ^0) giving nearly identical slopes [$\nu(\text{cm}^{-1}) = 1331.40(\pm 0.41) - 8.68\sigma$; $r = 0.981$] with *para*-substituted compounds only. But the position of the *m*-nitro above the regression line (not shown) with other *m*-substituents lying just below the line was again revealing. As anticipated, *m*-nitro derivative could be smoothly accommodated with other *para*-substituents when enhanced values for nitro and cyano groups were utilised [$\nu(\text{cm}^{-1}) = 1331.27(\pm 0.26) - 5.49\sigma$; $r = 0.984$] (Taft σ_R values gave poorer correlation coefficient). IR data therefore completely corroborate our conclusions based on the visible bands ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition).

Solvent Effect on the visible band ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^$ transition)* : The known¹² dipole moments of I, II and III are in the following decreasing order, III > II > I. One may therefore argue that any perturbation on the delocalised sextet through solvent interaction would tend to be resisted leading to hypsochromic effect on λ_{\max} in a polar solvent. Using the unsubstituted compound (III, R = R₁ = Ph) as a prototype of the series, λ_{\max} was exactly found to follow the known order of dielectric constants of the medium as shown in Table III.

11. J. E. Leffler and E. Grunwald, "Rates and Equilibria in Organic Reactions" John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1963, p. 171.
12. E. A. Braude and F. Sondheimer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3754.
13. H. H. Jaffé and M. Milton, "Theory and Application of Ultraviolet Spectroscopy" John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1964, p. 406.
14. Yu. G. Borod'ko and Yu. K. Syrkin, *Opt. Spectry* (USSR), 1961, 11, 261.
15. For leading refs. along similar lines, see, (a) T. L. Brown, *Chem. Rev.*, 1958, 58, 531; (b) F. Gerson and E. H. Heilbronner, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1959, 42, 1877.

But the results are somewhat at variance with Kosower Z-scales¹⁶ when isopropanol was used as solvent. Perhaps, additional steric factor arising out of *gem*-dimethyl group tilted the balance in favour of acetonitrile or the effective contribution from the solvent might be compensated through self association of the solvent. Furthermore, by using a series of acetone-cyclohexane mixtures as solvent, λ_{\max} shows a regular red shift with increasing proportion of cyclohexane in the mixture (Table III) and a perfect linear relationship was found to hold good between $1/\lambda_{\max}$ and composition of the mixture. The calculated λ_{\max} (442 $m\mu$) in cyclohexane, obtained from the intercept of this linear relationship, has been utilised in testing the extent of solute-solvent interaction ($\Delta\Delta E$) as stated above.

Fig. 2—IR spectra of C-S bonds of two typical members.

Although the long wavelength band in III is essentially $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ in character, yet the observed shift in polar solvents runs counter to the usual concept of solvent action on $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The situation could be reconciled with appreciable amount of double bond character in the exocyclic C-S bond leading to solvent action on non-bonding orbitals of sulphur, and the resultant shifts are therefore typical of those associated with $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions¹⁷. A fairly close analogy is found in the reported¹⁸ UV spectra of N-substituted hydrazones.

16. E. M. Kosower, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3253.

17. Ref. 12, p. 178.

18. J. A. Barltop and M. Conlong, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 1082.

From the results in Table III it is also clear that magnitude of this interaction is predominantly H-bonding type in hydroxylic solvents. Parallel behaviour has been recorded in the case of phenol betaines¹⁹.

UV Spectra : Coming back to the absorption bands in the UV region it is necessary to point out that only one band around 275 $m\mu$, except in the case of 5-*p*-MeO-Ph derivative (III, R = Ph, R₁ = MeO-Ph), was reported⁵ by the previous workers. But we consistently noted that the 275 $m\mu$ band ($\epsilon \sim 18,000$ to 20,000) was usually preceded by an almost equally intense shoulder around 250 $m\mu$ except in the case of *p*-nitro derivative (Table II). Aryl sydnone also exhibit² benzenoid bands in the 240–290 $m\mu$ region ($\epsilon, \sim 10,000$), and biphenyl¹³ itself shows a single band at about 252 $m\mu$ ($\epsilon, 18,000$).

The fact that intensities of these bands are so high compared to benzene bands in the same region, but comparable to biphenyl, strongly indicate that these bands are in all probability similar to ${}^1L_a \leftarrow {}^1A$ transition and the corresponding ${}^1L_b \leftarrow {}^1A$ transitions are possibly submerged in their trail. If this assumption is correct, then greater sensitivity²⁰ of the primary band (1L_a) to substitution pattern would allow us to assign them to appropriate phenyl groups.

It is thus readily comprehensible from the data in Table II that change in polarity of the substituent at 5-aryl group affects the λ_{\max} around 275 $m\mu$, but presence or absence of λ_{\max} around 250 $m\mu$ is totally dependent on the nature and position of the substituent on the aryl group. This could be readily reconciled from symmetry consideration of the phenyl ring at 5-position. For instance, with *m*-nitro derivative, relatively higher dissymmetry of the phenyl ring magnifies the 250 $m\mu$ band to such an extent that the other band is hardly perceptible, but the opposite effect is found with the *p*-nitro derivative. But two distinct bands emerge with *m*-ethoxy derivative and these meaningful changes are clearly shown in Fig. 3. Hence it is difficult to escape the conclusion but to ascribe the shorter wavelength band ($\sim 250 m\mu$) to phenyl ring at C₅ and the other band ($\sim 275 m\mu$) to phenyl ring

Fig. 3—Substituent effect on the UV spectra of three typical components.

19. J. P. Saxena, W. H. Stafford and W. L. Stafford, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1579.

20. Ref. 12, p. 258.

at N_4 . This is also supported from the consideration of the observed near constancy of the ratio of the intensities of the two peaks around $275\text{ m}\mu$ and the longest wavelength band around $400\text{ m}\mu$.

It is now perhaps possible to draw some attention to the extent of aromaticity in III in the light of its known properties. Thus, X-ray studies²¹ on closely related mesoionic thiazolium compound (VI) in conjunction with the high order²² of dipole moment, moderate intensities²² to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, absence²² of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, and the observed substituent and solvent effect on III are apparently compatible with some loss of planarity as well as appreciable amount of double bond character of the exocyclic C-S bond. Looking it from another point of view, dipolar forms (VII) are anticipated to be more important contributors to the resonance hybrid of III.

Thanks are due to Sri P. Bagchi, Research Director, for his keen interest, to Dr. S. Banerjee for helpful discussions and to Dr. S. K. Dasgupta, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-32, for recording the IR Spectra.

Research and Development Division,
East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd.,
119, Biren Roy Road (West), Calcutta-61.

Received July 31, 1968.
Revised MSS received April 23, 1969.

21. M. Garry Newton, M. C. MacDaniel, J. E. Baldwin and I. C. Paul, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1967, 1117.
22. For relevance of these parameters with reference to planarity in aromatic Schiff's bases, see V. I. Minikin, Y. A. Zhdanov, E. A. Medyantzeva and Y. A. Ostroumov, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, **23**, 3651, cf. C. M. Lee and W. D. Kumler, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 2052.